

[XXX] InterviewKey:

I: Interviewer
R: Respondent

I: **Okay, so it is now turned on. So the first question revolves around your position with [XXX]. I wondered if you could speak to your position and some of the tasks that you perform in the organisation?**

R: Okay. So I'm one of the [XXX] project managers. I've been with [XXX] quite a long time so I tend to get a lot of the specialist (recording inaudible 0.00.31) projects. I do a lot of European projects and then I do some large-scale evaluations. So currently in the UK we have a scheme called [XXX] which has put some money into various mental health and wellbeing initiatives and we're running the evaluation for that, so I'm project manager for that. I do quite a lot of gender projects and various other things. So it's the odd projects that maybe don't fit into our core work that I tend to end up with, for a number of reasons. Although I'm a member of staff I mainly work from home so that works to have those niche projects, and also I work part-time because I've got quite a young family, so I manage my own time around that, that's my role.

I: **Excellent. So was this the role you had when you initially had or has it changed over time?**

R: It's [laughs] changed quite a lot over time. [XXX] is part of a bigger organisation and the big organisation is called [XXX], and [XXX] have a wider remit than [XXX] do around career development in all kinds of formats across all kinds of fields really, we do lot of work in particular with STEM careers. So I had a role with them and I had a role with them working in schools and looking at how schools manage career development. And then over time, through various means, the [XXX] contract has grown and grown so there's been a need for more project managers on that and now the [XXX] contract makes up the majority of what we do within [XXX], because that's been the big growth area around researchers, so I've moved into that role. I've managed various programmes within that. I did a lot of training of researchers directly projects and now I do, like I say, these larger overview projects.

I: **Do you know all the members of your network, so all the members of [XXX]? Do you actually know them?**

R: Well we have about, I think, 150 member organisations, so no. The short answer is no. I do know lots of them, a lot of them tend to come to our conference, so I wouldn't know them all. I probably (unclear 0.02.57) know more than I think I do. We have the member organisations and then we also have a network of associate trainers. [XXX]'s quite a small organisation at the core but what we do is pull in expertise for specific projects, so we have a network of about 40 associate specialists that we work with, so I know most of them. I know quite a lot of the members but not all of them, particularly not our international members, as much as I'd love the trip to Australia to meet them it's not likely at the moment.

I: **You said most of them come to your conferences. Are they annual conferences or...?**

R: Yes, so we have a number of events that are member-specific and I think for your purposes where I talk about members that's probably what you mean by 'our network'. So it's a balance for us and one of the tricky things between our members is we're an organisation for all but we have to give value to our members. So one of the key ways that we give value to our members is in discounts from our big conference, so we have an annual international conference, so they have a discounted rates at that, and then also we have some specialist member events that we put on throughout the year.

I: **So in terms of the interpersonal relationships that you might have with some members, do you think personal ties play any role at all? What do you think the role of personal ties is in [XXX]?**

R: I think they do. Some institutions are members because another benefit of membership is a lot of our content is on our website which is resources that they can use in their institutions for members only. So for some institutions it's quite simple: they want their content or they want the discounted rate of the conferences. So therefore it is cost-effective to buy the membership to get that information and those resources. Other members join because they want to be part of – and I think this is the interesting stuff for RRING - part of the community that develops the agenda. So we have great [XXX] working groups and what you tend to find is you get the same kinds of people who join those working groups, which might be around what we can do (unclear 0.05.17) around a topic, so mental health and wellbeing or researcher recognition, so I think that's where the personal relationships work the best and where you tend to get real value. So yes and no for us, I think.

I: **So in terms of [XXX] has historically evolved, can you just give me some insight into -**

R: So, [XXX] was founded 50 years ago and it had a very broad remit. It was around career development for individuals and looking at how people reach the best potential within their careers. And then within that... I'm trying to think of the dates. I think it was 20 years ago, [XXX] won a contract to look at researcher careers because there was starting to become this challenge of researchers not fulfilling their potential, either not being successful as researchers or not being successful outside of research. The money was called the [XXX] Money and what [XXX] identified was that people did PhDs but nobody looked at their skills along the way, so nobody thought about how they were working as communicators or were they good problem-solvers and were they able to get funding. And there was nothing around those other things that once you've done your PhD... Can you sell your research to people? Can you stand up and present your research to other people? And it was purely around doing the work, doing the thesis was how people were assessed, so we were brought in to run a range of initiatives around developing researchers as a whole.

So they were things like residential programmes looking at skills initially, and then over time we started to look at more embedded solutions really around training people within institutions to train their researchers. So (recording inaudible 0.07.14-0.07.18) most institutions have a team of people looking after the researchers and looking at the research careers and research development. So what we tend to do now is more support those people rather than do the (recording inaudible 0.07.28-0.07.30) we support the people in the institutions.

So our original money was for UK only and I think we had ten, 15 years of that and that was a government pot of money to do that work. And UK universities' funding was restructured and we were asked to move to a membership model. So it was

almost that we're giving the institutions the money themselves and they can buy in your services. So that's been quite a challenge in terms of some institutions used to have something for free and now they have to pay for it – that's one way of looking at it. But equally, it's just that the money has been shifted and the really good side of that was it enabled us to look at the rest of the world, and what we realised was that researcher development in the UK is quite advanced compared to lots of other countries. So therefore a lot of the stuff that we'd been doing there was a real appetite for in Europe and America and Australia and now we're moving into Japan and Asia, so it opens up new networks. That's one of our key tensions really: supporting our members whilst also looking at expanding into other networks.

I: You initially mentioned that you're one of the project managers at [XXX]. I also wonder if you could speak to what other roles you have within the organisation, because I'm thinking around things like the division of labour within the organisation, so as a project manager your tasks might practically revolve around research like you (unclear 0.09.11) initially but what other roles do you have within the organisation to manage some of the projects that you work on or even the activities of the organisation moving forward?

R: We're quite a small team so we pull together in lots of ways really. I would manage my own projects' finances, we'd look at comms and dissemination of them. I've got a bit of background in training development so I might work with the training development team to develop training. We have a small senior management team of four people so I work a lot with them around strategy and so on going forward.

I: What is the legal structure of [XXX]?

R: So we're a registered charity but – and this is where I get confused sometimes – by being a charity it really means that we're not for profit, so we don't make profit rather than we're going to donate to anything particularly. So we have a board of directors who are external whose job it is to keep track of the legal side of things, and then we have a small senior management team and then the rest of us.

I: Why do you think this network model was chosen, the structure, do you think there was a rationale behind having it this small?

R: I think it's just been need really. We need to be quite lean as a core team and responsive to the projects. So like I said, we have this membership funding model, but then we also have a project spending model which tends to be European Horizon 2020 work, commissioned pieces, that kind of thing. So it's about being able to be agile to the work that we get really and making sure that we can put the right team in place for specific projects whilst also being quite lean in terms of our core team. As I said, it was quite a transition from going from core funding to this new model, and I think we're just coming through the other side of that really now. So certainly we've expanded more over the last couple of years. We've started to build up again but we did have quite a big staff reduction in order to build back up.

I: You've clearly spoken to the advantages of the model that you have, but what are the limitations? What are the cons of this structure? Are there any potential limitations that you have encountered?

R: I think a real challenge is providing value to our members. So offering an attractive organisation to work with and offering value while not locking content away. So for example, our website is what do you make for members and what do you make for non-members, but equally in order to be attractive people almost need to see the

content, to see what you can offer. So if you lock everything away then why is anybody interested in working with you? But equally, if you don't give value to your members... So for example, the conference (unclear 0.12.13), the price point you want to make competitive, so somebody in Holland who's interested in your work can come and see what you do, but equally if you offer that for the same amount as a member pays, what's the point of being a member? So I think we've got a bit of a tension and this is moving from the old model to maybe a new model in terms of how we manage and serve our member community who perhaps demand more from us than the non-member community, but equally understanding that if an... I think our membership is £1000 to £6000 depending on the institution size. So there's a sliding scale. Ensuring that we add value to that...

And also I think because we've got some members who used to get things for free they're probably much more demanding than our newer customers. So to them, a new price can look much more expensive than to a new customer.

I: Yes, because obviously they've never paid for it in the past.

R: Yes. I don't know whether RRING would look to... People paying for stuff is good because it ties them in, it shows commitment, and by doing that it locks people in and they expect something. So they make a decision to join rather than just saying they'll join. So the payment is good but the balance is tricky.

I: Diversity and gender are frequently discussed topics. At [XXX] would you say that plays a role?

R: Yes. I think it does. Our mission is to develop researcher potential and we know that female researchers have some issues in that area and there are some limitations for them so we've done a lot of projects around gender, in terms of (unclear 0.14.05) and where we stand on it and where we stand as advisers to policy really. So yes, we do play a role. Just out of interest, our core staff is predominantly female. I think it's a job that does appeal to females maybe more than males so that's something that we're constantly trying to readdress. But if you look around our network, researcher developers are also predominantly female, so yes that's a challenge that we're continuing to work on and look at really. I think it's key to the success of research, keeping that at the forefront.

I: So in light of that would you say that awareness of gender and diversity contributes to the success of your network? And if you would agree with that statement the question then is how has it contributed to the success of your network so far?

R: Yes, I think it absolutely does. For us, it's around developing tools and resources that people can use to address that in their own institutions and having a stance on it. We have a [XXX] Excellence Award that we award to institutions around researcher [XXX], so there's a checklist in there around how... To get that award an institution would have to show awareness of (unclear 0.15.33).

I: I'd like to speak a little bit more about the members of your network and the membership model. I know you have [overspeaking] that in some detail but I'd like to explore that in some depth now. So what are the range of membership options that you have?

R: We have an option for individual members. A researcher could be a member but we don't get much take-up on that, it's highly unlikely that anybody would do that but we

have it as an option should somebody be an interested researcher in an institution that doesn't have membership. And then our membership model ranges from £1000 to £6000 annually for an institution membership, and that very much depends on the size of an organisation. It's a stepped level around your number of researchers.

I: And do network members have things like voting rights or decision-making -

R: No, they don't have voting rights or decision-making on [XXX]. Like I say, they have specific member events, they have reductions on some events for all, so for example the conference, they have access to website information and quite a lot of our content is locked. So like I say a lot of them are in it for that resource really, that updated content and training courses and so on that they've in effect bought into. And they also have some tools, particularly on the Researcher Development Framework, which are member-only.

Alongside that, if they're a member organisation we do a lot of policy work. So for example at the moment we're rewriting the concordat to support researchers in the UK, for the UK, in line with industrial strategy – a government piece of work. And members would be asked to comment on that and have the opportunity to develop it, so be hands on around that.

I: Okay, so these are the reasons why members actually choose to join -

R: [overspeaking] Yes and then there is some feeling of, and again this is something to explore for RRING I think, there are certain things that are good to be seen to do, so joining things like CIPD and other organisations. If you're interested in the wellbeing of research it should be seen as a good thing to be part of. But how you explain that to people is trickier.

I: I wondered if you could speak to things like joining CIPD, how would that... Because as you mentioned, that has an impact for RRING and I wondered if you could perhaps shed some more light on your thoughts on that.

R: I think it's just there are certain organisations in certain professions, and we've explored this a lot at the moment with researcher development, whether you should be part of that body. It's seen as an authority and it's seen as the right thing to do, and to be a good researcher developer or to be a university that is interested in researcher development, you should really have that membership. So for example things like the Equality Charter, there are certain things that it's a good thing to do and I think that's one of the things we're working on: to continue to influence the sector, really an institution should be part of it. And although £6000, maximum, is quite a lot of money, it's not a lot of money – it's less than one student's annual fee.

I: Okay, so I have some more questions on some corporate managerial questions in particular, things around governance and the management structure, but also how some of the funding sources you employ are actually implemented. Some of the questions I have here you have answered so I am going to skip them but there are questions that I think we could explore in some further depth. So, in terms of [XXX]'s annual budget, does the network have a long-term budget projection? Or do you, in the first instance, know if [XXX] has an annual budget?

R: We do have an annual budget, yes. I can't remember off the top of my head how much it is. I think we only project the next two years, or it might be three years. I don't

think we do as long as five years, just because the sector is quite fluid and that would be quite tricky to do, but yes we do have an annual budget.

I: So is it safe to assume from your answer that the reason why [XXX] doesn't have a long-term budget projection is just because of the nature of this sector in that -

R: Yes, I think so. As I say, I think we probably have a two, three-year plan, but it's semi-structured, with a constant look to the sector around... A lot of our work is European for example at the moment and that is very hard to predict going forward, so yes, it's we think these might be sources of income but we keep looking (unclear 0.20.56)... It's quite easy to predict where we want membership to go, we have this many members, do we want that to go up, do we want it to go down – it's more around the project work. So yes we do and it's something we key into quite clearly really, looking across the projects at the finance and so on.

I: And how important is funding to the network?

R: Sorry, I lost -

I: Okay, sorry. I said how important is funding to the network? I'm trying to explore the amount of resources that you as an organisation actually spend on securing funding?

R: Yes. So like I say we're funded through project work which could be European government, specific organisations. I'm doing a big piece of work at the moment with IPO around intellectual property for researchers and trying to (unclear 0.21.56) intellectual property, so various things, and then we have our core membership funding as well. It's really important to continue in our work. The project side of things, that's for a specific customer group. So whilst it enhances our learning, a project should pay for itself really. The membership is really what funds the network and the ability to inform government or inform the sector or do gender equality work and so on.

I: So can you tell me who has managing responsibilities for the network?

R: It will be our chief executive who is [XXX].

I: So you have a chief executive. Do you have a board of directors or is it just -

R: We have a senior management team who have that higher level strategic overview, and then we have an external board as well.

I: Can you explain the board? Who are the members of the board? How is that board constituted?

R: It's various industry experts, so it's people but people with a specific interest in the topic but it's their job to govern the senior management team.

I: Regarding communication, do you have regular management meetings and how frequently do you have these?

R: There's a monthly senior management team meeting and then we have a weekly staff team meeting.

I: And how do you measure or monitor the effectiveness of the network?

R: Now is quite an interesting time because we're just coming round to membership renewal so that's a key way that we monitor the effectiveness, if we buy back in, if we get feedback from people and so on. We have a membership community that we monitor to see what people are saying around our work, and then it's through conversations we get a good feel for it. We've done a couple of member sessions at the international conference to get a feel for whether we're providing member value. We ask members to get involved in telling us what they want us to produce for them, what the sector's asking for. So there's no real strategic questionnaire or anything, it's more around ongoing conversations and, like I say, that membership renewal time is a really key time for understanding whether the members have had value over the year.

I: You mentioned that [XXX] doesn't have a five-year budget plan, but do you have a five-year roadmap for instance, some action plan (unclear 0.24.40) projecting the plan for the next five years? So this is more tied into anything to do with finance, but concrete points of action for four, five years. Do you have that sort of roadmap?

R: Again, I don't think it would be five years, I think probably three years. So we have a roadmap and we have ideas around different pots that we would see funding coming from and things we want to do for the network and so on, but again it's light touch because we have to be more agile than that really.

I: And is it possible for us to (unclear 0.25.18-0.25.20) the plan but is this publicly available?

R: I don't think it is. The best thing to look at, and I'll send you a link after this, is our annual report, and there will be a new annual report out in September which is when our conference is which will coincide with that, but I'll send you the link to last year's annual report which will give you all those headline figures and so on and explain some of this stuff for reference for you.

I: Do you have a risk and mitigation plan?

R: We do. We have to include it in quite a lot of... Again, I'm not sure... We have a general one for the organisation and we draw one up for specific activities. I'd have to see...

I: Hello?

R: Hello. Sorry to (unclear 0.26.22-0.26.23). I can have a look and see if I can get hold of that for you, I'm not sure if it's shareable but I can ask if that would be helpful.

I: Yes, that would be helpful. The other thing around the plan is I'm assuming that you... Are you saying you're unsure if you have one or you do have one but you do not know where it is presently?

R: Sorry, can you repeat the question? You've broken up a little bit.

I: Okay, sorry. Is it fine now?

R: No, it's fine.

I: So I was saying with regards to the risk and mitigation plan, are you saying that your organisation doesn't have one or it has one but you're just not quite sure where it is being housed?

R: It has one, I'm not sure if it's publicly available to share – that's my query. I know we have one, again it would be part of the role of the board to discuss that with... I just don't know if it's a confidential document or not.

I: So [XXX] has one. Do you have any insight or inkling as to how it is monitored?

R: It would be monitored by the board through their regular board meetings, and I think our head of finance would have to prepare a report on it every year or so.

I: A governance issue is often the distribution of information or knowledge as a main driver for people to be part of a network, so how we disseminate information to members of that network. Can you describe how information is made available and circulated among the members of [XXX]?

R: Sorry, can you repeat this again? This phone line is breaking up all over the place, I lose where I am and I'm still struggling a bit to hear you.

I: Is it better now?

R: No, it's a bit worse to be honest. It was fine at the start and it's gone a bit to pot.

I: I'm still sat in the same place.

R: I didn't move and then it started to go strange.

I: Shall I just end the call and give you a ring back and see if it's better?

R: Yes, let's see if that makes it any better, thank you.

I: Okay, I'll do that now, thank you.

R: Bye.

[call ends and resumes]

R: Hello again.

I: Hello. Is it better now?

R: Loads better now yes, thank you.

I: [laughs] I have no idea, I'm still sat at the same place. [laughter]

R: It's the old-fashioned just turn it off and start it all again, isn't it?

I: [laughs] Yes. So I was wondering if you could speak to how information is made available to members of the network?

R: Yes, so we have a newsletter which comes out every two weeks I think to our members. We also use a lot of social media, so we use Twitter as well, and then for

specific information for members or opportunities for members, we can contact them directly so we have an email system where we write to them directly.

I: The fact that you mentioned social media here actually (unclear 0.29.41-0.29.42) for me to explore a little bit further. In light of that I wondered if you could speak to whether the use of social media has actually improved engagement with members? Has there been any such thing or has it just been the status quo?

R: I think particularly Twitter yes, because it's so instant. The good thing is about Twitter is when people are using it at events you get a flavour for how the event is going on the day because you can see the Twitter conversations going on during the speaker and so on. So I think with Twitter absolutely, I think that's the key one really. So yes, I'd say so. It depends because some people don't touch it so for some people not at all, but for lots of people yes I think so and it's great for that immediate messaging.

I: And do all network members receive the same information irrespective of their membership type?

R: Yes.

I: Fantastic. So what would you say are the general issues that affect effective governance and what do you think would be needed to further improve the management structure that you have?

R: It's tricky. I think the management structure we have works really quite well. Our challenge is around the fluidity of what we do and particularly at the moment our big challenge is Brexit like lots of people around, how much we can plan, given we were doing a lot of work in Europe, how much we can plan on that continuing. So I think that makes effective governance tricky. And then I also think it is that tension between balancing our members, tying people into that network which is great but ensuring that they get value for it. And balancing, and RRING probably won't have this as much, but we are UK-based and we were initially for the UK and the majority of our members are from the UK so balancing UK versus international too and their needs because for us a lot of the UK work is much more advanced than what we're being asked to do in Europe.

I: And that nicely leads to my last question. You in your answer mentioned the challenge or one of the challenges was Brexit, but I also wonder if you could speak to any other challenges that you think the network encounters or will potentially encounter moving forward?

R: I've mentioned the membership one quite a lot. This will be a challenge for RRING, it's the nature of different countries and what they need, and making sure that you do something for all, so making yourself appeal to everyone is difficult because a lot of the (unclear 0.32.39) work is around is the European definition the right one? And hopefully we'll have some good ideas at the end of it. But say on a website you lose too much of that you might start to look less relevant to other people. So I think there's a real challenge with global networks, having things everybody agrees on but having enough flexibility to go 'Yes, I know that won't work in your country but we'll do it this way there and that will work really well.'

I: Your answer speaks to this notion of cultural differences and differences in nations and collectivity and collaborations sometimes, as a consequence of people's cultural, national identities, things like that. Have you found -

R: Yes, and alongside that the structure of research in... Some places are very competitive in culture, they don't like collaboration because that's how their research institutions work, which obviously is a challenge then for (unclear 0.33.43). So yes, there are a number of factors at play there and I think it's very tricky to get that, this is what we do that can be clearly useful for everyone whilst also allowing that flexibility and not dictating about how it should look for a specific country.

I: **And have you found instances where individuals have joined your network or as a consequence of XYZ you uncover that there then become problems with those members (unclear 0.34.11) their own identity as institutions prior to joining your network? So the identity they had initially and the identity that they as a consequence of becoming a member of XYZ, the identity that emerges is one that is slightly counterintuitive to their ethos. Have you found that? Have you encountered that initially?**

R: We don't tend to with new members, we tend to with older members [laughter] to be honest. I would say we tend to with the historic ones who almost feel like they can dictate the agenda. New members tend to buy in and get what we're doing and they want the materials and so on so not so much. But you do get that with older members who maybe look to do things a different way. There is a challenge there because with a university like for example [XXX] in London, for what we do, researcher development, I think it has got 15 researcher developers, it's got a big department of people just for that institution, doing what we do. And is that okay to let them go and do that? So a lot of the training courses and things won't appeal to them because they're building their own in-hour stuff, for them the value is only in the network, but making sure that has value for them compared to a little institution in Lithuania who just doesn't even know where to start with training their researchers is tricky. So I wouldn't say so but I think balancing the cultures is tricky and making sure that the conversation fits everybody is difficult.

I: **And are there cases where network members have dropped out?**

R: Yes.

I: **And why did they drop out? Did they give any reason?**

R: We don't get loads, we've been quite pleased about that, but it comes up to membership renewal time and that's where somebody says 'I'm not paying that again.' When they do, it tends to be around them not seeing the value of the network, so perhaps not engaging. Sometimes it's they haven't been engaging with the events or the materials and therefore they cost cut. Sometimes it's a new member of staff who doesn't see the value. It tends to be around that. Sometimes actually a good conversation with them can sort it out, around what the value is. Other times not. I think there will always be a bit of coming and going with those things but we hope that they could see the value, but yes, sometimes not. You only need a new finance person who says 'I'm not paying for that.' [laughter] 'I don't see what that's for.'

I: **And have you encountered situations where there have been conflicts between members of the network and their affiliations with different organisations?**

R: I wouldn't say there's conflict. Yes, there's a bit of challenge around there are other organisations that do... So for example in the UK (unclear 0.37.30) are doing an event on mental health and wellbeing for researchers next week. So I think for us it's around making sure that we just work with those organisations. We're quite niche in

what we do. What we need to be doing is talking to other people that could be seen as competitors so we're all on the same page around it. Like I say there can be a little bit of conflict there but generally it's okay and we keep talking to people and seeing if we can work together on things. That's the key, where there could be conflict it's ironing it out with other organisations.

I: So if you could warn up about any potential pitfalls, dangers to guard against, what would these be?

R: Around the network?

I: Yes, around creating a network of responsible research organisations.

R: The pitfalls are not being clear on what the advantages are to the people joining the network, so it's really taking the time to be clear on what those advantages are, from all of the stakeholders' perspectives. And making sure that maps inter-culturally.

I: If we're going to be creating a network that is going to be broader than the UK, what kind of tips would you give us on trying to ensure that we create (unclear 0.38.59) where it is not antagonistic to different cultural stereotypes and consequently which would affect membership moving forward? How do we manage that?

R: It's about being really flexible about the approach, so not being dictatorial in this is how we do it. This is the core, this is what we're trying to do, and having a really flexible approach to how it might work in other countries and being prepared to learn from other countries. So having the key principle but then equally being prepared to learn from other countries unless they're being very, very flexible in approach around what might work. I think the key thing for RRING is what will come out of the research. I think at the moment it's trying to answer something that potentially we don't (unclear 0.39.51), what is coming out from those other regions and how can we address it, but within those regions there will be tension and difference. I think it's trying to be clear about what we do whilst not trying to tell them how to do it.

I: I also wondered if you could shed some light on whether or not you know any network that is doing what RRING is proposing to do presently?

R: I don't think there's any... Not globalist as far as I know.

I: And do you know of any locally?

R: There's things like the RRI Tools community that are worth looking at. Have you looked at them?

I: No.

R: Okay, if you look at RRI Tools, they're mainly around resources but they have a network and their network has grown up really around their resources. The other network that's really interesting to look at is (unclear 0.41.00). It was originally around mobility for researchers so it was set up to make it easier for a researcher in Paris to move to Croatia to continue their research, almost like a big jobs board: 'I'm a nuclear physicist, I'm particularly interested in this, I see there's an opportunity somewhere else in Europe.' So it's around social mobility but it has been a real success, it's worked in about 40 countries and it's started to go more global, and yet it does have some core funding, but in terms of the network and the way they do their

network events it's a strong and growing network. They've done some European outreach to other regions, so it's interesting to look at them.

I: Okay, fantastic. Many thanks for your time [XXX]. We've gone through the questions that I have on the guide, but I also wondered if there was anything else you'd like to add in terms of perhaps your thoughts, some concerns you have, or even just some ideas that you'd like to share which would help us achieve our objective of creating this network?

R: Yes, I think what we need to be clear on what we're looking to do as a network. Is it chatrooms and webinars? Is it it will meet this often? Is it all online? How are we looking to approach the network? I think people like that concrete side of it. It's not the main thing but I think that should be thought of in conjunction, what are we saying that a network will do and how will it do it? Otherwise people sign up and they get a newsletter and nobody really reads it and what does it look like as a network and what is it trying to achieve. It's tricky, I think it's doable, but I think there's a lot to think about with it.

I: To my mind, when I think about this, I think it just sticks to the problem of clearly articulating what the problem is that RRING is trying to sort out, what the gap is, and then tailor solutions to addressing that particular gap. So where I struggle a little bit is trying to figure out or identify what that problem is that is accepted universally, not from an international perspective, not from a European perspective, not from a UK perspective, but from a global perspective, what that problem is that we will address. Would you say that speaks to some of your thoughts in terms of -

R: Yes. If I'm at university in Kenya, what are the benefits to me of joining -

I: [overspeaking] Absolutely, yes.

R: And I think that's what often means these things can be a bit too top down, and it has to be, like you say, what will it do. And for them it's still going to be about quality of research, it's going to be about funding, opportunity – that sort of thing, making their researchers better.

I: Towards articulating the problem, the phrase you use here is having an approach which is too top down in how you actually go about uncovering the problem. How would you recommend or advise that we adopt some sort of bottom up approach towards ensuring that power is situated with individuals we would ordinarily engage with, towards ensuring that their thoughts, their opinions actually inform how we construct the problem? How do we achieve this?

R: Well I'm hoping some of that will come out from the regional work that's going on, and then I think it has to be speaking, it has to be focus groups with those people or using the network to feed that back to us, so using the consortium to gather some really clear data around what would work for an institution in their region. So I think we have got the consortium so it might be a questionnaire for them or it might be asking them to find a local institution and go in and find out something like that. But I think that's the thing: they need to be clearly able to explain why it would... These people are busy, it goes without saying. Why would they join and why would they give that time and how is it going to improve their daily life?

I: Fantastic and many thanks for sharing your thoughts with me [XXX], it's very much appreciated -

R: [overspeaking] No problem.

I: And so this concludes the interview. Once we have outcomes of the interviews and we have the reports we will be sharing that with you so we'll keep you in the loop so you are aware of the outcomes that emerge from this project, but again many thanks for your time and if you have any questions at the end of the interview, if there are any issues that you'd like to explore further or some questions that you might want me to answer, then by all means please feel free to either call me on this number or just send me an email and I'll be happy to get back to you.

R: Okay, lovely. I'll send across that report because I think it'll help where you do your writing up, and if there's anything else you think of just give me a call or drop me a line and I'll try and help if I can.

I: Fantastic [XXX], thanks very much, I appreciate it.

R: No worries, thank you.

I: And have a nice day, bye.

R: Good luck (unclear 0.46.46), thank you, bye.

(End of recording)